

Laser Processing of Thick-Walled Composite and Composite-Metallic Structures

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ABSTRACT

Studies were conducted to evaluate the effectiveness of using high-power laser beams for cutting and drilling holes in thick-walled composite and composite-metallic structures and to study the effects of welding metallic members in the vicinity of composite metallic joints. A 25 KW continuous wave carbon dioxide laser, producing an intense beam of infrared radiation at a wavelength of 10.6 microns, was used for the studies. Laser output was fully programmable and controllable from a threshold value of 1 KW to a maximum of 25 KW, including ramp-up, ramp-down and extended continuous duty cycles, thereby permitting parametric variation in power input (pulsed and steady state) to the process. A system of reflective optics was used to direct the beam for focused or defocused penetration for burrowing through or trepanning operations. Materials used for the evaluation included glass, aramid (Kevlar) and graphite fibers with epoxy and polyester resin systems and high strength steel for the composite-metallic structures. Composite structure thicknesses up to 2 inches were investigated. For broad beam drilling, the heat of combustion generated delaminated zones in the composite matrix surrounding the penetration. Comparisons are made of the relative delamination, as well as the quality of penetration, distortion and other degradation of the material over the power input range for the material systems investigated.

